

Distributing Solar Physics Data

Minimizing Wasted Bandwidth

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Abstract—The solar physics community archives most of its data using the FITS file format. We discuss advantages and disadvantages of FITS files, particularly as related to transfer of data across the internet. We suggest small changes to archives that manage FITS files, and techniques that could be used by sites that mirror these files. We discuss the need for a more holistic approach in designing and implementing solar data systems.

Keywords—scientific computing; data transfer; data storage systems; distributed information systems; astrophysics

I. INTRODUCTION

New solar missions are producing data at a steadily increasing rate. Keeping up with today's space-based solar data can almost saturate an OC-3 (Optical Carrier 3; 155Mbps). Although some groups may need access to all data from a given instrument, the vast majority of researchers only look at a portion of the available data. Additional bandwidth is wasted in re-transferring of FITS files when only the headers have been updated.

We describe the current state of transferring solar data over the Internet and steps that could be taken to build a comprehensive solar data infrastructure and mitigation that can be done with our current data systems to reduce bandwidth.

II. DATA VOLUMES

Although storage costs have decreased over the past few years, the volume of solar data has increased such that the cost of storing and transferring the data are still significant costs. Network speeds have improved, but are still a critical bottleneck in transferring large volumes of data.

The fastest growing publicly distributed solar physics dataset is from the Atmospheric Imaging Array (AIA) on the Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO). AIA takes eight 16-megapixel, 16-bit images every 12 seconds. The result is 32 MiB of sensor data, which Rice compresses at roughly 3.4:1 after level 1 calibration. The resulting 524 GiB/day is distributed to multiple mirror sites in the U.S., Europe and Asia. To keep up with new data, a site needs to be able to sustain 50 Mbps without any interruptions. This requirement doesn't seem like much with today's gigabit-ethernet, but the US FCC currently defines broadband speed as only 4Mbps.[1]

As none of the mirror sites have the ability to store the entire archive, currently around 800TiB, they maintain 'rolling archives', in which the older data is cleared out to make way for newer data. If a scientist wants older data, the archives need to transfer the data again. It is quite common for scientists to analyze a month's worth of data, in either one or all wavelengths (roughly 2TB and 15.6TB, respectively per month). For some sites, it may take a week or more to re-acquire the requested data in addition to keeping up with the flow of new data.

We also must consider that most sites will want other data. At the Solar Data Analysis Center (SDAC), we also get data from Hinode, IRIS, SDO/HMI, SOHO and STEREO, and may have other bursts of data transfers from moving complete archives, as we recently did for Yohkoh and TRACE. In some cases, such as the transfer of the final TRACE archive, it's faster to ship hard drives rather than transfer the data across the internet. As this process is more labor intensive, we typically reserve physical shipments for one-time transfers, rather than ongoing data streams.

Things will only get worse as the Daniel K. Inouye Solar Telescope (DKIST, formerly ATST) is commissioned, the Visible Broadband Imager is expected to produce 960 MiB/s of raw data. [2] If they can get similar compression to AIA, the resulting 2.2 Gbps would effectively saturate an OC-48.

III. FILE FORMATS

As a community, we're in good shape when it comes to file formats. Most current projects use the Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) file format [3] for their lower-level data, which can be read by wide variety of software tools.

To change to another file format would require significant changes to both archives, to the existing software tools used by the community. It is doubtful that the man-hours required to re-write software and re-validate data could ever be cost effective compared to work-arounds to deal with issues that exist in FITS, as described in this paper. As such, the only other file format that we have analyzed is VOTable[4], which was designed for interoperability with FITS, but which would still require modifying the majority of the tools used by the solar physics community.

Higher level data products, such as event catalogs, are in a much more varied formats. Although standardizing could save researcher time and make some science easier, the transfer of

these files is insignificant compared to the volume of FITS files.

15. UPDATING METADATA

One of FITS greatest strengths is that by keeping the metadata within the data file, every image can be self-documenting. From a data management perspective, this feature creates a logistical headache, as to correct the metadata risks corrupting the data if we update the file, and the need to re-distribute the updated file to any mirror sites. As such, some PI teams avoid updating the headers, requiring scientists to use other methods to get up-to-date metadata; these work-arounds undermine the advantages of using FITS.

Although the metadata in the files has grown over the years, the size of the data portion of the files have been increasing much faster, as sensors have gone from 1 megapixel as used on the Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO) to 4 megapixel for Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatories (STEREO), to 16 megapixel for SDO. The SOHO and STEREO instruments listed have operating modes do not send back full sensor images or reduce the data before downlinking; while STEREO and SDO use Rice compression. As such, the filesizes do not scale linearly with sensor size.

TABAE I. HEADER SIZES

Detector	Average File	Headers	
	Size in MiB	Size in kiB	% of File
SOHO/EIT	1.68	8.4	0.492
SOHO/LASCO	2.15	8.4	0.383
SOHO/MDI	3.53	8.4	0.233
STEREO/EUVI	8.00	19.7	0.240
STEREO/COR2	6.65	19.7	0.289
STEREO/HI2	4.26	19.7	0.452
SDO/AIA	9.41	16.9	0.175

Due to the headaches of transferring the large volumes of data, most solar physics data files are not updated, even when the metadata is known to be inaccurate. Instead, PI teams distribute catalogs with corrections for clock drift or pointing precision, as done for the Transition Region And Coronal Explorer (TRACE), or as calibration software, as is done with telescopes and coronagraphs on SOHO and the two STEREO satellites. For these missions, the raw images are distributed, so that any future calibration can be applied without the need to re-transfer.

It is exceptionally rare for the structure of the headers to be modified after the initial embargo period. Although new FITS standards may be published, the PI teams avoid changing the files, both for reasons previously mentioned and to avoid breaking existing tools that may use the files. As such, active instruments such as from the 18 year old SOHO mission do not follow any of the clarifications made in later standards, and will not be updated until the 'final archive' is generated after the instruments are decommissioned.

Much of the data transfers between mirror sites in our community is currently done by rsync, scp or wget. As scp and wget operate on whole files, changing and header value requires re-transmitting the entire file. Rsync can transfer only the portion of the file that has changed, but increases disk i/o and CPU as it computes checksums for segments within the file. If the size of the header has increased, it will end up transferring the complete file.

In the case of Hinode, new headers were added just before the embargo was lifted, requiring re-transferring multiple months of data. Attempting to do this transfer across the Internet required saturating the SDAC's network connection for weeks.

We have two main ways to attempt to mitigate this problem: keep the metadata separate from the data, so the metadata can be updated independently, or find a way to transfer only the portion of the file that has changed.

A. Transferring only metadata : TRACE

During the active mission, the PI team distributed catalogs to correct metadata, including the pointing and timing metadata for their images. These files were distributed as Interactive Data Language (IDL) save files and, thus, were unusable for those people who may not have an IDL license or were using older versions of IDL as their save files were not backwards compatible.

This method also allowed for lazy transfer of the data; as remote sites had the catalogs to the data, they could search through the metadata and transfer files that were of interest.

After the mission ended, the 'final archive' was generated, which generated data files containing the best-known metadata. This required re-transferring the entire archive.

B. Transferring only metadata : NetDRMS

NetDRMS is derived from the Data Record Management System (DRMS), [5] the system built for managing Helioseismic and Magnetic Imager (HMI) data from SDO and also used for AIA. It uses a relational database for the scientific metadata, allowing it to be modified without touching the FITS files on disk. The metadata is mirrored to other sites using database replication, allowing near real time (NRT) updates of metadata to sites participating in the network at significantly reduced bandwidth.

In the case of HMI data, no scientific or engineering metadata is stored in the FITS files. As designed, the system should never need to update the files on disk, but means that the files must go through an 'export' process to be used for analysis with other tools.

AIA data is also stored in DRMS, but their PI team only uses DRMS for their processing pipeline; so they can use their own analysis tools, the files are stored with the initial metadata in the FITS header. Researchers should still use the NetDRMS 'export' tool to ensure that no metadata modifications have been made since the file was written, much like the system that was in place for TRACE.

Currently, no tools exist to update a file from DRMS in-place. The exported files lack sufficient identifiers to be able to make a generic tool that could query DRMS for updates

through their existing APIs; a tool could be developed to use other metadata from the existing exports, but it would need to be updated for each new published series, particularly if those series have corrections for clock drift. With sufficient identifiers in the exported files, such a tool could be more easily developed. Adding checksums to the exported files to allow such a tool to verify files before and after updating.

C. Transferring only metadata : VOTable

VOTable [5] is an XML-based file format developed by the astronomical community as a replacement for FITS. It has headers composed of keyword/value pairs similar to FITS, but also allows additional attributes to provide additional semantic information. VOTable also allows for files that reference data in an external file through what they call 'FITS serialization'. Rather than store the data within the file, the file contains a URL to download the data separately:

```
<DATA><FITS extnum="2">
<STREAM encoding="gzip"
href="ftp://archive.example.edu/myfile.fit.gz"/>
</FITS></DATA>
```

This method allows for metadata to be updated without needing to modify the original data files, but may result in unexpected results, as handling mis-matched metadata is specifically undefined:

The VOTable specification does not define the behavior of parsers with respect to this doubling of the metadata. A parser may ignore the FITS metadata, or it may compare it with the VOTable metadata for consistency, or other possibilities. [4]

VOTable could be used to share metadata changes between archives, but to get widespread use in the solar community would require modifying existing analysis tools to read VOTables and retrieve FITS files on demand.

D. Transferring partial files : diff and patch

We can't use the standard `diff` and `patch` commands to generate a report of what changed within the file as they report on changed lines; the lack of line feeds mean that the whole file is considered to have changed. (footnote: inserting line feeds or carriage returns into a FITS HDU will not pass the FITS Verifier [6] If this trick were allowed, you also want to add sufficient blank cards to move END to end of the 2880 byte block, so you can extend the HDU later.)

Luckily, the astronomy community has built a FITS aware `fitsdiff` [7], which can report on the differences between two FITS files. Unfortunately, the underlying PyFITS library requires very strict validation of FITS files and will fail for minor problems that ftools, iraf, DS9 and other tools treat as warnings. Currently, a lack of tools apply the modifications (aka `patch`) to a given file.

`diff`-like programs that operate on binary files exist; jojoDiff [8] can extract the modifications, but it provides no context; only the characters that have changed within the file are in the report generated. We may be able to get around this problem by creating FITS files with embedded checksums [9,10] The checksum ensures a value will be known in the file to be modified, and we have a way to verify that the changes were applied correctly.

Attempting to generate diffs of files does require keeping two complete files while generating the report. If this code could be inserted into reprocessing pipelines, we may avoid accumulating significant amounts of duplicate data on disk.

E. Transferring partial files : HTTP

Transferring partial files doesn't actually require coordination between the archive and mirror site, if the files are available via the HyperText Transfer Protocol (HTTP). Most modern web servers support the 'Range' header when serving static files. [11] This technique allows us to request only the first 2880 characters of the file:

```
curl -H'Range: bytes=0-2879' 'http://stereo-ssc.
nascom.nasa.gov/data/ins_data/secchi/L0/a/
img/euvi/20070312/20070312_000742_s4euA.fts'
```

We can request ranges from anywhere within the file, so it's possible to request the next 2880 blocks if we haven't found the END card or extract a sub-header from the middle of the file.

This technique on its own doesn't allow us to verify that the data has not been modified, but combined with the DATASUM header [9,10] can allow us to check whether we should retrieve the full file.

5. LAZY TRANSFER OF DATA

Sharing just the metadata headers allows researchers to more easily verify that the data is suitable for their purpose before attempting to download it. This advantage not only saves the time and resources of the research, but also can dramatically reduce the bandwidth used at an archive.

Catalog systems like that from TRACE or NetDRMS can allow us to share detailed descriptions of the data, which the researchers can then load on demand as needed. Through the use of database triggers, NetDRMS can be configured to automatically select files for transfer without human intervention.

The Virtual Solar Observatory (VSO) is built around a similar model, in which a researcher can search, get back a record describing matches, and then select which data to download. [12] What the VSO does not currently do is give the complete FITS header; metadata is homogenized to an internal data model that may not have information that a researcher may wish to use as a rejection criteria. This lack of metadata can result in downloading of data that is immediately discarded after transfer.

There are other trade-offs to lazy transfer, such as researchers will need to wait for the data. As we frequently have requests for a month's worth of AIA data, this amount can mean over 15 TiB to transfer, which would saturate an OC-3 for 5 days. If the data is no longer online, this type of request can cause additional delays as tapes need to be loaded and read. We expect this problem to continue, as network speeds are not growing as quickly as our data rates.

5I. FOR THE FUTURE

A. FITS Checksums

The most important way our community can improve our management of data, would be to include checksums within

our files. There is a registered extension for storing checksums within FITS files [9,10] which allows us to verify whether the file may have been corrupted either in transfer or was affected by bit rot while stored.

Checksums are especially important as the data may be re-processed in multiple places, rather than re-transferred. In the case of AIA, the data being distributed has intentionally not undergone any irreversible transformations, allowing the original calibration to be backed out and a new calibration applied. A catalog of checksums from all calibrations would allow researcher to verify that the initial inputs were the same and that the resulting output is the same without the need for re-transferring the data.

B. Global Identifiers

If the solar community could agree on standards for uniquely identifying data files, tools could be developed to check the authoritative source if the file has been deprecated, and potentially correct or replace the file as appropriate. Such an identifier system could also be used to link to unambiguously link between different processed forms of the data, providing provenance information to ensure reproducible science.

We believe that this could best be done using a collection-level identifier that is unique within the community, and then a more granular identifier to distinguish between files or observations within a given collection but may not be globally unique. This two level system would enable tools that could generate appropriate attributions for the data, allowing for better linkages between the data, documentation for the data, and publications that use the data.[13]

C. Sharing FITS Metadata

We next need to decide on a community standard for sharing of FITS header data without transferring complete files and retool our analysis tools to support it. This strategy may mean adopting VOTable[4], transferring only the header portion of the FITS files or coming up with a hybrid approach to make a valid FITS file but replace the data portion with a URL or other actionable identifier for retrieval of the data.

D. Universal Solar Data Infrastructure

As a community, we should attempt to standardize on a comprehensive infrastructure. Standardization could allow sites to download from anyone who had a given file and verify the checksum against the PI's copy, rather than need to download from the PI or project archive every time. Such an infrastructure would also simplify connecting new sites that have or want data, as we make a single connection to the infrastructure instead of needing to coordinate connections with every other site that may want your data or have data you want.

A number of systems in use by other research disciplines, either as 'data grids', distributed object stores, or simply lower level transfer protocols. As these programs have been developed over years or decades, they are robust, stable systems with well-established communities of support.

We should discuss what type of services are needed to support our science and find the system that best meets our needs without significant overhead. Do we need something for

just pushing around bits like GridFTP[14,15] or do we need authentication and data abstraction layers from something like iRODS[16]? Can we use data systems such as NOAA's CLASS[17] or OODT[18,19] as-is or would we need specific modifications to deal with issues for our data?

E. Review of Data Management Systems

Technologists from other solar data systems have specialized knowledge about managing solar data that the PIs and project management would not have. So that we can identify potential problems before systems are built, the data system reviews should include people with practical experience in data modeling, system administration, software engineering, database administration, digital archiving and computer security. To better gain even better diversity, it may be worth including reviewers from other research communities other than astronomy and space physics.

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